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The Social Problem of Single Mothers in Europe

Introduction

The social problem of single parents in European countries had become more statistically visible in the 1990s (Bradshaw et al. 2000; Kennedy et al. 1996), with projections to 2025–2030 suggesting a further increase. In the decade between 2009 and 2019, the number of single adults with dependent children increased from 12% to 14%. The sociodemographic profiles of single parents in have changed during the last decades, along with changes in their conditions and experiences. At present, single parents no longer consist mainly of widowed men and women or single mothers, but now mostly comprise separated or divorced parents, particularly mothers. Single parenthood is still significantly gendered: for 11% of households with children, the single parent is a woman, while the 3% is a man (Nieuwenhuis 2020).

In such countries, single parenthood is perceived as a social problem due to its dimension, increase, gendered characteristics, impacts on the well-being of single parents and their children, and the difficulties involved in creating and implementing adequate policies. Due to its gendered characteristics, this social phenomenon is often described as the “single mothers’ problem.” Even if their conditions seem to be less stigmatized than in the past, single mothers still suffer from a lack

of resources, employment, and adequate policies: a condition that is called the triple bind of single parents (Nieuwenhuis and Maldonado 2018).

Comparative studies indicate that the “single” status, even if sometimes transitory (due to the repartnering phenomenon), interferes heavily with many trajectories of vital life domains. The major negative outcomes for these parents are represented by poverty, unstable or insufficient/unrewarding employment (e.g., difficult conciliation between child care and work), and poor health. The presence of these and other factors also resulted in single parents’ diminished ability to recover from stresses in different life domains when compared with other types of families (Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018). To date, there are numerous studies on single parents’ social conditions and analyses of policies that either contribute to or mitigate negative outcomes.

However, datasets present limitations, and many authors have underlined the need to better monitor single parents’ conditions.

This chapter provides an extensive examination of recent studies across European countries. It illustrates insights, evidence, and arguments concerning the characteristics of single parenthood, how it is defined and measured, its main negative outcomes, how policies try to mitigate these outcomes, and the aspects that should be improved in the future. Then, the chapter offers possible directions for future research, arguing the need to understand the global characteristics of this phenomenon in a comparative way while simultaneously considering their local variations and highlighting how life course studies might assume a key role in improving policies.

Definitions of single parenthood

In everyday discourses, until the mid-1990s, people referred to a “single parent” as a widow or as someone who had children born outside marriage. While the first one was an acceptable condition, the second one was often stigmatized. In the second decade of the 21st century, people may refer to a “single mother” as someone who never married and has raised her child or children alone without

a partner or as someone who became a single parent after the dissolution of a marriage or cohabitation with a partner. The first situation is less stigmatized, whereas the second one is very frequent and not often perceived as a kind of single parenthood (Letablier and Wall 2018). Changing definitions over time reflect changes in the sociodemographic profiles of single mothers and families during the last decades (Trifiletti 2007; Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018). Aware of the cultural differences and social transformations that have contributed to the different meanings given to single parenthood over the years, sociologists have drawn on varying definitions of parents in order to describe the complex universe of single parents and parenting, which includes separated, divorced, widowed, and single parents. Differences in conceiving single parenthood in many societies reflect varying cultural and gender representations of the family and single parenthood, wherein the first reference still seems to be the traditional nuclear family formed by a mother and a father and their child/children. Yet, according to Letablier and Wall (2018), the reference to the “traditional” nuclear family is no longer valid, as a great variety of family arrangements can already be found throughout European countries.

The sociological literature provides different definitions for “single parents.” Among these, the most accepted definition is provided by Duncan and Edwards (1997, p. 3), who stated that single parents’ families are those “where a parent lives with his/her dependent children, without a spouse/partner, either on their own or in multi-unit households.” However, this definition raises certain issues for comparative research (Letablier and Wall 2018): how and when children can be considered as independent, when a living arrangement can be considered autonomous, and when and how to define a mother as someone “without a partner” while considering different official or non-official relationships after separation or divorce. Different studies and national governments have applied heterogeneous criteria to these three aspects. For example, the definition of children as “dependent” can be linked to the cultural context and/or the purposes of a specific research study. Letablier and Wall (2018, p. 31) pointed out that a broad definition—often present in most surveys—considers single parents as “those who do not cohabit with a partner, whether they have

support from other significant persons, be they non-residential partners, ex-partners or others.” Not satisfied by this very broad definition, these authors have proposed an original definition reflecting the current family transformations in European countries. They used the terms “*single* single-parent family” to define a family wherein children do not see the non-residential father and “*single bi-parental* family” to refer to a family wherein children are used to sharing time and residence with both parents. This definition is based on the criteria of sharing time and home with the non-residential father. In any case, a “*single bi-parental* family” poses the problem of having two parents who are counted twice as single parents due to the shared residence with children.

Toulemon and Penneec (2010) underlined the difficulties of collecting and interpreting data in situations wherein there is a shared residence. A classic example of this issue concerns the problem of determining whether a single parent comprises a full-time or part-time household. Legal decrees or informal arrangements after divorce or separation create complex situations that cannot be easily translated into statistical and sociological terms.

Other authors (e.g., Chzhen and Bradshaw 2012) used a more extensive definition, which also includes parents who live in multi-unit households. Bernardi and Mortelmans (2018, p. 3) defined single parents as “single living adults in the age range of 15–55 with children aged 18 or younger present in the household.” The same authors used the term “*included* single parents” to refer to single parents living with their parents or in a non-independent household. The issue of the “*included*” single parents needs attention, because in some datasets the “*included*” single parents are, for example, teen mothers who continue to live with their parents. The conditions of such single parents comprise a phenomenon that has yet to be fully examined.

To summarize, data about living arrangements and other conditions that characterize single parents’ families are sometimes difficult to collect, analyze, and interpret correctly due to the heterogeneity of definitions among time, countries, and current studies. This problem becomes particularly evident in comparative studies.

Overview of the phenomenon

Despite the difficulties in analyzing and comparing data about single parents, in the last 30 years, the social problem of single parents has become increasingly statistically visible. Many studies have confirmed the rising numbers of single parenthood throughout Europe and, therefore, of single motherhood through different data sources (Nieuwenhuis and Maldonado 2018; Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018; Nieuwenhuis 2020a).

Bradshaw et al. (2000) and Kennedy et al. (1996) conducted the first studies that showed the initial changing evidence of this social problem. In statistically describing the prevalence of single parenthood, differences are noted among the sources used in Europe and in other OECD countries. Among other sources, Eurostat offers the most comprehensive overview of single parents in Europe, even though it also has certain limitations, which will be discussed later. In 2018, among all European Union (EU) member states, 15% of households with children were single-parent households. The lowest percentages of single-parent families can be found in Croatia (6%), Romania (7%), and in Greece, Slovakia, and Finland (all 8%). The higher rates can be found in the Nordic countries, including Denmark (29%), Estonia (28%), Lithuania and Sweden (both 25%), and Latvia (23%), along with the UK (22%) and France (21%). In 2019, the overall percentage decreased by one point, reaching 14.1% among the EU member states. The lowest rates of single parents were found in Romania, Croatia, Montenegro, Serbia, Turkey, and North Macedonia (all less than 7%), as indicated in the study of Nieuwenhuis (2020a). In addition, Letablier and Wall (2018) analyzed the OECD 2011 Family Database and found that Greece, Spain, and Italy presented the lowest rates of single parenthood in correlation with high incidences of marriage.

Even if studies have frequently highlighted that single parents are mostly women and that men comprise only a very small percentage, these studies did not provide detailed and articulated discussions about the distribution among genders. As the Eurostat indicators are based only on the criterion of “single adults with children,” such data do not differentiate single parents by gender and

whether they are biological or social parents. Thus, such data do not allow the identification of child(ren) who live with both parents when they are separated (Nieuwenhuis 2020a). Furthermore, most of their datasets differ because of the sources that they utilize; in particular, the most common sources are the international surveys LIS (OECD 2015), OECD 2011, EU-SILC (Iacovou and Skew 2011), PISA (Chapple 2009), and ECHP (Chambaz 2001). Despite the limitations of these datasets, a consistent body of research on single parents exists in Europe. However, only a few cross-country comparative studies are available (Letablier and Wall 2018), and the overview on essential aspects of single motherhood often lacks precision.

A recent report (Nieuwenhuis 2020a) considered trends in single parenthood based on different indicators by gender, providing detailed descriptions of single parents' conditions in 27 European countries from 2009 to 2019. From these data, the study clearly showed the gendered nature of the single parenthood phenomenon: women comprised 11% of single living arrangements against the 3% recorded for men in 2019. Some EU member states in that period showed an increase of single mothers and fathers as a result of the application of the law on shared custody of children and the inclusion of both separated fathers and mothers in the datasets.

According to Bernardi and Mortelmans (2018), the inhomogeneity in data of cross-country comparative studies can be attributed to the fact that children can be counted as dependents by the age of 15, 18, or 25 years. The same authors described a situation in which the length of single parenthood varies significantly across countries, but the age of the parents when they become single is commonly around 30 years old. Countries wherein the length of the single parenthood condition is greater include Switzerland, Georgia, Lithuania, and Russia. This phenomenon can be attributed to two factors: the role of the local context in facilitating or preventing repartnering and the age at which the divorce happens. In any case, the length of single parenthood also differs based on sex and the number of children aside from age. In general, the repartnering possibilities have increased from the 1950s until now, which is a sign of the changing status of single parenthood and that it is now less stigmatized than in previous years. An analysis conducted on recent cohorts of single

mothers showed that they can find a new partner within two to four years. In comparison, studies on older cohorts showed that this period used to be within 8 to 10 years (Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018). Recksiedler and Bernardi (2019) suggested that repartnering has been interpreted as a strategy that can help single mothers improve their economic and personal situations.

A study in 11 European countries (Gałęzewska et al. 2017) described the levels of repartnering and the characteristics of women who repartner, with the aim of understanding whether women's demographic characteristics under union dissolution and repartnering conditions are similar or different across countries. The study concluded that regardless of country, it is less likely for older women and/or mothers to start a second union.

Even if single parenthood is often considered a “transitional step” in the life cycle because of the possibility of repartnering, it must be noted that such a possibility depends on the local contexts or on the age at which the divorce happened (if applicable). Furthermore, in some countries, highly educated single parents have a better chance for repartnering, whereas in other countries, single parents with an intermediary education have better opportunities (Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018). Based on gender, the length of single parenthood is a major factor for women but a minor one for men, and this is probably due to the differences in custody arrangements. Thus, changes in the law concerning the shared custody of children in many European countries might also change these data in the future, in which the repartnering of women might be similar to that of men. For example, research conducted by Pasteels and Mortelmans (2015) in the Flanders region using individual and dyadic data pointed out that the presence of children from the first marriage affects the post-marital relationship trajectories of divorcees. Their findings also showed that mothers are less likely to start a new relationship and that repartnering dynamics appear to be driven by children's living arrangements. Furthermore, other studies (e.g., Regnier-Loilier et al. 2009) highlighted the effect of policies on repartnering: sometimes women may prefer to maintain welfare benefits and preserve their independence through an LAT relationship. Gałęzewska et al. (2017) showed through data that the presence of children either reduces women's attractiveness in the partner market or their

willingness to bring a new partner into her family. A qualitative study in four European countries (Tartari 2019; 2021a; 2021b) concluded that the phase of transition from double to single parenthood concerning judicial decisions should be better considered as a crucial moment in shaping single parents' trajectories.

Single mothers' problems: Work, poverty risks, and health

When the literature focuses on specific problems of single parents, the gendered dimension becomes very evident. Single mothers represent 84% of single parents, and being a single mother is a strong predictor of unstable employment histories, poverty, poorer health, and lower life satisfaction (Pollmann-Schult 2018). The single parenthood condition has been shown to interfere with several life domains (Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018), even though this status is transitory. Single mothers' problems in terms of health, employment, living conditions, migration, life satisfaction, and poverty risk are more frequently discussed in the literature. Past studies have also highlighted the short- and long-term effects of the single parenthood condition and its length on their life trajectories. Large-scale surveys have shown that negative outcomes (poverty, unemployment, and poor health) represent higher risks for single mothers who have a weaker ability to recover from stresses in different life domains (Bernardi and Larenza 2018). This chapter will consider the three most discussed areas, namely, work, poverty risk, and health, and the negative outcomes that affect them.

Work

Many studies, including comparative studies, on the relations between European single mothers and employment are available. The capacity to participate in the labor force is poorer for single mothers compared to women who cohabit with a partner. Past studies have shown that younger mothers and those with younger children or with more than one child face even lower possibilities of working or

maintaining a stable job (Millar 2010; Ruggeri and Bird 2014; Hancioglu and Hartmann 2012). Furthermore, single mothers who are employed often have to choose between spending time at home with children and working for a sufficient income (Ruggeri and Bird 2014). When countries have proper work policies, single mothers are more likely to work full-time (Plantenga et al. 2010). OECD countries and Scandinavian countries have all posted a female employment rate of over 60% (OECD 2011). Employment rates of single mothers increased in European countries between 2009 and 2019 from 69% to 74% (Nieuwenhuis 2020a). However, more of these single mothers have a part-time job than women with partners or single women who have no children (Ruggeri and Bird 2014). Many studies have also shown that single mothers are less educated (Härkönen 2018) and, therefore, are less skilled and have lower-paying jobs than other mothers (Stewart 2009; Zagel 2014; Zhan and Pandey 2004). Therefore, when they meet the hidden costs of employment, such as financial costs for child care, transportation costs, and fewer hours for direct household needs (Bauman 2002), these women are more likely to leave the labor market or to be stuck in a low-paying job. These conditions relate to the social benefits effect that may sometimes appear to be negative in terms of determining whether single mothers are less prone to increasing their participation in the labor market (van Damme et al. 2009). Cultural factors also affect the aspirations of single mothers, which may be oriented toward active participation in the labor market or major care of their children (Gingerbread 2012; Bell et al. 2005; Boeckmann et al. 2014). However, a study conducted in Switzerland (Struffolino et al. 2020) on the employment trajectories before and after the transition to single parenthood highlighted the high degree of heterogeneity of these trajectories. The study reveals that single mothers' employment opportunities and participation in the labor market are related to how they started their single parenthood; their relationship with their ex-partner; their skills in activating individual, social, and family networks; and other institutional resources. The authors concluded that attention should be given to the differences *within* the group instead of emphasizing the divide *between* single and coupled mothers.

Poverty Risks

Single parents are considered a risk group for poverty (European Commission 2007; Van Stolck et al. 2011). In fact, across the EU, children who live with single parents are at a greater risk of poverty or material deprivation compared to those from two-parent families (Chzhen and Bradshaw 2012; Nieuwenhuis and Maldonado 2018; Treanor 2018; Nieuwenhuis 2020a) with a risk of compromising resources for the children's future.

In European countries, the at-risk-of-poverty rates for single mothers range from 7% (Poland) to 37% (Latvia). The highest risks can be found in Eastern European countries, such as Lithuania (32%) and Hungary (31%), as well as in Ireland (29%), Spain (27%), and Italy (27%). The lower risks have been reported for Sweden (15%), Norway (16%), and the Netherlands (16%), according to past studies (OECD 2011; Hübgen 2018; Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018).

The rate of *in-work poverty* among single parents is greater in comparison to coupled parents, with European countries showing great heterogeneity in the decline (e.g., Lithuania, Luxembourg, Cyprus, Bulgaria, and Spain) or in the rise (e.g., Hungary, Malta, Ireland, Estonia, and Belgium) of in-work poverty (Nieuwenhuis 2020a). In-work poverty is a common phenomenon among workers in elementary occupations, but it is less common in countries with stronger employment protection measures (e.g., concerning the use of fixed-term contracts, temporary work agencies, better-paid leaves, expenditures on child care, and expenditures on active labor market policies). Some authors (e.g., Nieuwenhuis 2020a) reported that these families received more income transfers than they paid in taxes over their earnings. Life course studies (Tsakloglou and Papadopoulos 2002; Vandecasteele 2011) have also demonstrated the accumulation of disadvantages for the social groups that are already vulnerable to other factors, such as lower levels of education, precarious employment, and neglected health. In these groups, episodes of single parenthood exacerbate work factors like low-paid jobs and part-time work; family factors like non-proper personal, familiar, and social networks; and institutional factors like inadequate child support payments (Zhan and Pandey

2004). Therefore, the accumulation of disadvantages deserves attention, especially because it has a major role in the formation of poverty risks.

Divorced single mothers are not exempt from poverty risk. A study (Hübgen 2020) has shown the relationships between poverty risk and single mothers' social characteristics (e.g., employment status, age, and number of children) and institutional contexts (e.g., family and labor market policies). Single motherhood has a poverty-enhancing effect for divorced women, which seems to decline from the second year after the divorce, despite instances of other single mothers experiencing a more stable effect. However, regardless of the time, geographic areas, or methodology of the studies, all studies of the past five decades confirmed that women are disadvantaged compared to men, especially after divorce or separation. Data from past studies also showed that economic losses and poverty risk as the equalizing effects of joint custody are not yet visible (Tamborini et al. 2015; Mortelmans 2020). In conclusion, children of single mothers have a much higher risk of social exclusion or poverty compared to those with two parents (Lopez Vilaplana 2013).

Health

Bad health conditions have been firmly associated with poverty and social inequality (e.g., Mackenbach et al. 2008) and, consequently, with single parents' health status (Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018). According to past studies (e.g., Kühn 2018; Struffolino et al. 2016), exposure to chronic stressors in multiple life domains contributes to single mothers' poorer health trajectories compared to coupled mothers (e.g., Avison and Davies 2005; Wickrama et al. 2006; Cooper et al. 2008). Other studies highlighted worse general health conditions (Whitehead et al. 2000) and an increase in mental health issues (Crosier et al. 2007) among single mothers. The reasons for their worse health conditions are mainly related to the higher levels of psychosocial and financial stress that characterize the single mothers' status (Recksiedler and Bernardi 2019). A lack of support from the social network (which often decreases after the separation/divorce) and having unstable or low-

paying jobs also affect the health trajectories of single mothers, sometimes independently from institutional welfare contexts (Burstrom et al. 2010; Dziak et al. 2010; Nieuwenhuis et al. 2018). Even when the welfare state intervenes consistently in supporting single mothers, there remain negative effects of the synergy between single parenting and non-employment or low-paying employment on single mothers' health trajectories. Studies emphasized the role of policy regimes as well as culture and traditions in the emergence of single mothers as a vulnerable social group (Fritzell et al. 2007; Van de Velde et al. 2014).

Policies for countering the negative outcomes of single parenthood

Many studies have attempted to identify which policies work better in supporting single parents in Europe, how they can reduce or mitigate single parents' vulnerabilities, and the processes by which the inequalities characterizing their life trajectories are formed. Some studies have offered suggestions on how to improve or develop more appropriate policies. The first part of this section is dedicated to the review of current policies and the second one to a review of suggestions for future policies.

Current policies

In order to reduce or prevent poverty risks, welfare states use tax breaks, family allowance supplements, advances of maintenance payments, child care benefits, social assistance or housing supplements, and income supplements for single parents (OECD 2011). There is an ongoing debate among scholars who support the effectiveness of universal measures and those who support the need for policies targeted for the specific social group of single mothers (Treanor 2018; Kenworthy 2011; Marx et al. 2016). Welfare transfers (universal like in Sweden or means-tested like in the UK) seem to be more helpful for single parents compared to those policies that are specifically designed for them (Maldonado and Nieuwenhuis 2015; Van Lancker et al. 2015; Bernardi and Mortelmans 2018). In addition, social assistance at different levels has been proven to be ineffective in many

European countries and has declined progressively as a measure (Nelson 2011; Cantillon et al. 2016).

Only a few European countries have family benefits that are specifically targeted toward single parents. These countries offer single parents a combination of universal benefits and a supplement for their specific condition. Other countries have a poverty-targeting policy model that supports families classified as “impoverished” under specific criteria that are not only directed toward single-parent families. Countries that use specific targeting policies within universalistic measures tend to have the lowest poverty rates among single parents (Treanor 2018): given that single mothers have different characteristics than other parents, a policy strategy that is effective for a subgroup of single mothers appears to be ineffective for single mothers of a different subgroup. Countries tend to have the best outcomes in reducing poverty when benefits are based on the single parent *status* and not on their incomes (Morissens 2018).

Cash transfers and benefits are extremely effective in reducing the poverty risks of single parents and their children (Bradshaw et al. 2018). Related to these last measures, there are policies concerning child support (also known as “child maintenance”), which enforce the financial responsibilities of the non-resident parent (often the father) for their children. Child support policies in the EU member states are considered complex (Nieuwenhuis 2020a) in their determination, and with a great variation across EU countries. This kind of income can make a great difference, particularly for single mothers. Studies have shown that if these mothers could receive all the child support payments to which they are entitled, poverty rates of this social group could be halved. However, the impact of this measure is smaller than that of child benefits, because the reality is that the majority of single parents do not receive such payments; therefore, this measure is associated with moderate to small reductions in poverty rates (Hakovirta 2011; Skinner et al. 2012; Nieuwenhuis and Maldonado 2018). The process of claiming these payments is complex (e.g., going to court, hiring a lawyer, cooperating with other institutions, etc.). When public institutions can give these payments in advance on behalf of the defaulting parent, it can be an effective

instrument in reducing single parents' poverty (Gornick and Smeeding 2018). Child support policies also have a limitation in the sense that they may no longer reflect the increasing family transformations and differences in current society; thus, child support is often calculated based on assumptions that may be incorrect depending on each situation (Nieuwenhuis 2020a; Claessens and Mortelmans 2018). Furthermore, child support payments may be subtracted from other benefits (e.g., means-tested benefits) received by single parents (Hakovirta et al. 2020), thus reducing the positive impact of the measures on poverty risk. Finally, there are possible paradoxes between child support policies and policies that aim to reduce gender inequalities (Skinner and Hakovirta 2020; Nieuwenhuis 2020a).

Providing child benefits has been described as an appropriate measure in tackling poverty risk, particularly if such a policy targets single parents (Bradshaw and Finch 2002; Van Lancker et al. 2015; Maldonado and Nieuwenhuis 2015). According to Nieuwenhuis (2020a), child benefits are effective in reducing poverty in in-work single parents but with some paradoxes: if they are received through tax benefits, then higher-income families receive higher benefits, essentially defeating the purpose of poverty reduction in families with single parents who may have periods of unemployment. Furthermore, unemployment benefits and minimum income protection policies seem to be ineffective in protecting this kind of family (Cantillon et al. 2018).

Nieuwenhuis (2020a) pointed out that early childhood education and care (ECEC) is considered the most important policy in promoting gender equality in the labor market (e.g., Misra et al. 2007).

When implemented appropriately, it can facilitate the employment of single parents and reduce the risk of poverty for children. However, some studies have reported that its socially stratified application mostly failed to reach the children and families who are most in need. Paid parental leave has great potential in increasing the employment of single parents and in reducing the risk of poverty; however, about 10% of mothers are not eligible for statutory paid leaves because of their unstable work situation.

States can encourage parents to become part of and stay in the labor market through “active” labor market policies that also include income support and assistance in actively searching for jobs or staying in the labor market. These policies are also present in strategies that target single parents. However, scholars have warned against the adoption of “active” social policies aimed at achieving welfare provision by facilitating employment (Nieuwenhuis and Maldonado 2018). These active social policies result from the social investment framework, which aims to enhance the economic independence of individuals and stimulate employment to reduce poverty, but they disinvest in welfare transfers as a way to counter poverty. Unfortunately, the outcomes of these social investment strategies seem to be the intensification of pre-existing inequalities that are associated with single parenthood (Pintelon et al. 2013), as they tend to benefit those with more resources (Ghysels and Van Lancker 2011). The paradigm of social investment has raised criticisms because it hides gender inequalities in the household and the labor market while simultaneously underestimating the costs of raising children and the value of care (Millar and Rowlingson 2001; Saraceno 2011). Thus, even if these policies successfully increase the employment rate among single parents, poverty rates among this population may not be reduced. Stimulating employment without ensuring cash transfer policies does not mitigate poverty efficiently when parents also have to counter street-level bureaucrats as well as hidden inequalities and gendered disadvantages for women (Cantillon 2011; Cantillon and Vandenbroucke 2014).

Struffolino et al. (2020) conducted a study on heterogeneity in employment trajectories before and after the transition to single parenthood in Switzerland and found differences in employment opportunities and decisions based on three crucial factors: how single mothers began their single parenthood, the quality of the relationship with the children’s father, and their individual, social, and institutional resources. They suggested that greater research and policy attention should be directed toward the differences *within* the group of single mothers rather than toward those between the families of single mothers and two-parent families.

In summary, at an empirical level, studies have provided evidence that universal welfare states can better protect single mothers against poverty risks than those that utilize targeting strategies; furthermore, single mothers are better protected with generous targeted child benefit systems and work-family reconciliation policies. At a theoretical level, a concept coined by Nieuwenhuis and Maldonado (2018) can help in understanding the intrinsic combination of the single parents' conditions and the role of policies: the concept of the *triple bind* of single-parent families, which is inspired by the *double bind* definition first introduced by Gregory Bateson and his colleagues in the 1950s. The triple bind concept suggests that single parents, particularly single mothers, face challenges from situations that are constantly evolving: their single parenthood in itself, the labor market, and the social policies related to them. The combination of these challenges—inadequacies in resources, employment, and policies—and their continuous evolution constitute the triple bind that affects these single parents' families. Single parents tend to be constructed by institutions through policy as “dependent, underserving, work-avoiding or a threat to social order,” thus reinforcing some disadvantageous and stigmatizing aspects of their conditions (Nieuwenhuis and Maldonado 2018, p. 421).

Suggestions for future policies

The literature on the impacts of social policies for single parents in European countries suggests two conclusions. The first one concerns the need to evaluate policies as a whole and the interactions among them, and the second conclusion concerns the need to well-estimate the role of the “universalistic policies” that seem to be effective in reducing single parents' difficulties and their impacts on the children's future.

Some studies have critically assessed the applications of social investment policies (explained in the previous paragraph), describing such policies as the consequences of emerging social risks. These social risks include the rise of single parenthood as a social phenomenon and the greater difficulties encountered by welfare states in countering poverty risks for single parents. Nieuwenhuis and

Maldonado (2018) argued that the inadequacy of policies becomes more evident when there is a gap between the assumptions of policies and the reality of resources and employment. They thus introduced the concept of the *social trilemma*—situation wherein governments have had to seek balance among budgetary restraint, inequality, and employment growth after the global economic recession that started in 2007. For example, the reasons for the structural inadequacy of minimum income protection for single-parent families can be found in this social trilemma. Moreover, European countries apply different combinations of these three dimensions in deciding and devising policies and interventions (Cantillon et al. 2018).

Nieuwenhuis (2020a) recommended improvements in policies with short- and long-term perspectives, highlighting the notion that stable social change can only be achieved with long-term policies. The *short-term policy suggestions* concern, first of all, aspects of child custody for separated parents, including enhancing the application of joint physical custody for separated parents, removing administrative and bureaucratic barriers that can impede the obtainment of benefits, and expanding joint legal custody (even if no clear empirical evidence has been presented on how it benefits children and parents). Second, employment protection legislation to counter in-work poverty must be improved in order to reduce the sense of insecurity among single parents. Third, states must guarantee advances in child support payments and exclude these payments from means-testing. Fourth, intending to reach equal and higher participation in ECEC, public provision subsidies must be strengthened, thus ensuring a place for each child and reducing out-of-pocket fees. Fifth, there should be flexible, well-paid, and non-transferable parental leaves to increase fathers' participation in child care. Sixth, the minimum income protection to reduce poverty risks must be raised. Finally, there is a need to reconsider the eligibility line (criteria and application procedures) for parental leaves and unemployment benefits, with the aim of making already existing benefits more effective. This is because most of these benefits are not being taken up due to the issue of non-eligibility.

Meanwhile, the *long-term policy suggestions* concern several aspects. First of all, gender equality in care and work must be promoted, as challenges for single parents have structural characteristics at work and at home, especially after the separation. This would enforce the responsibilities of fathers in care roles and alleviate single mothers' burden. Second, the diversity of families should be considered by promoting a *family diversity mainstream* (Nieuwenhuis 2020b). Single parents are single-income earners who have different needs and costs, but often, such diversity in two-parent families is not considered in analyses of policies. Third, following the suggestions of many studies, it is strongly recommended to not only propose employment growth as a means to reduce poverty risks but also consider other strategies (e.g., better quality jobs and keeping both welfare benefits and work incentives). Fourth, the monitoring conditions of the situation of single parents in European countries must be improved, as different problems may emerge concerning the indicators included in official datasets (e.g., Eurostat).

Studies (Morissens 2018; Van Lancker and Van Mechelen 2015) offered evidence and explained how the application of a universal child allowance (directed to all families with dependent children) combined with specific benefits targeted to single parents can improve efforts to counter the poverty risks faced by the latter. These scholars also highlighted that countries have been able to achieve greater success in countering the poverty risk and the triple bind of single parents by combining universal benefits with those targeted to single parents based *on their status* and not on their income.

Other studies have shown that single mothers are better protected from poverty risks when strategies are targeted toward single parents (Brady and Burroway 2012) and when generous targeted child benefit systems (Van Lancker et al. 2015) and work-family reconciliation policies (Maldonado and Nieuwenhuis 2015; Misra et al. 2012) are utilized within universal welfare states. Furthermore, Zagel and Hübgen (2018) suggested that policy analyses would benefit from utilizing a life course perspective. Specifically, considering single mothers as not just a “uniform claimant category” can lead to a more realistic scenario of this social group. Through a study conducted

across four European countries, these authors offered empirical evidence regarding the different forms of single motherhood in various phases of one's life course. Each of these phases includes different life course risks and welfare states' policies have different impacts on these varying stages and conditions. Thus, the heterogeneity of these single mothers' conditions should be considered during the formulation of policies. Zagel and Hübgen also adopted the notion of risk management systems to explain their finding: the condition of single motherhood is just one kind of risk that is associated with other risks that have varying degrees of relevance in each stage of the single mothers' lives. These authors illustrated how some policies seemed to have embedded restrictions on eligibility related to the age of the mothers, which changes at different life stages. All the countries they examined implemented policies with age restriction. Their most important finding is that the life stage in which single motherhood is more frequently reported by statistics (in each country) is not necessarily the life stage that presents the highest economic risk in a mother's life course. Furthermore, this stage is not necessarily the one that is better protected by the policies. Meanwhile, Struffolino et al. (2020) suggested that policies promoting single mothers' participation in the labor market should take into account their access to formal and informal networks, which can support them, along with these mothers' priorities (in terms of expectation) in reconciling work and care obligations. Finally, in a comparative study Sierminska (2018) pointed out how policies might contribute to the single parents' ability to build wealth, thus challenging common assumptions on policy goals.

Conclusion: Future research directions

Future research should be conducted to help unpack the data, processes, and practices that can solve or mitigate the triple bind faced by single parents. This paragraph provides directions for future research, as they emerged from the literature. It also analyzes suggestions and other aspects that remain open to debates, thus requiring further research.

First, Letablier and Wall (2018) suggested that the concept and definitions of single parenthood must be unpacked by analyzing the different sociological meanings derived from the datasets and indicators. They underlined the importance of conducting more research and refining theoretical frames, and demonstrated the potential of using the life course perspective in providing a dynamic understanding of the complexity of single parenthood.

Nieuwenhuis (2020a) underlined the limitations of the Eurostat indicators concerning the single parents' situation in EU countries, including those in terms of identifying the number of single parents, in differentiating them by gender, and in understanding whether the parent in one household is the actual parent. Furthermore, the author pointed out the absence of error margins in the estimates reported by Eurostat and the lack of consideration of recent changes in society, such as the spread of joint physical custody in many countries. Thus, the existing datasets present an inaccurate identification of the different kinds of single parents. Nieuwenhuis (2020a) argued that such limitations may have an impact on properly understanding the phenomenon of single parenthood and the adequacy of policies implemented. Thus, the monitoring instruments applied in the EU should be improved. In addition, Letablier and Wall (2018) emphasized the lack of longitudinal datasets and in-depth national and cross-national studies on single parents' life trajectories in European countries, along with analyses that allow a better understanding of the role of biographical and structural variables affecting different issues and are present across countries. Meanwhile, Bradshaw et al. (2018) suggested that the process of proving the identification of single parents in multigenerational households should be improved. Furthermore, Zagel and Hübgen (2018) underlined the need for more in-depth analyses and better measures of child maintenance, and better consideration for the single mothers' sociodemographic backgrounds in the period before the onset of single parenthood, given that these characteristics often have impacts on their eligibility for policy support.

Gornick (2018) also insisted on the importance of analyzing in-depth the complexity and diversity of single-parent families. In particular, more theoretical and empirical research should be

conducted to unpack the link between gendered aspects and practices (e.g., gender asymmetry and “gender specialization,” which are aspects that remain dominant in two-parent families) and the relative or total absence of fathers in many of these single-parent families. Furthermore, more research on single parents outside the OECD countries should be carried out, with the goal of comparing middle- and low- and high-income countries. Nieuwenhuis and Maldonado (2018) support this proposal, suggesting that future research should include more fine-grained data on local variations about single parents’ resources, employment, and policies (e.g., including cities, provinces, and urban and rural areas) with a global perspective. Furthermore, regarding the policy topic, they highlighted that future research should conduct comparative analyses of the issues of accessibility (e.g., eligibility), the uptake of social policies, and the quality of governance across countries. Qualitative studies may also facilitate the formulation of new hypotheses and theoretical explanations about processes and practices concerning different issues (Bernardi and Larenza 2018). Finally, Nieuwenhuis (2020a) pointed out the need to gain a better understanding of the socioeconomic impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic for single parents.

Acknowledgements

The author acknowledges the European Commission, as this chapter was written during the period of her Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research Fellowship awarded by the EC for her research project “Study on TRansition and Exclusion in Society of Single-Mums (STRESS-Mums)”. The project received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no 843976.

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